

A Study of Malaria-Related Pediatric Morbidity and Mortality in a Tertiary Care Hospital, Bihar

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 15-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Malaria continues to pose significant health risks to pediatric populations in tropical regions, particularly in Bihar, India, where it significantly impacts morbidity and mortality rates among children. This study provides a detailed examination of malaria cases at Patna Medical College and Hospital, focusing on understanding the demographic and seasonal patterns influencing disease transmission.

Methodology: A retrospective cohort study was conducted, analyzing medical records from June 2015 to May 2017. Data on 95 pediatric patients diagnosed with malaria were included, with a focus on demographic characteristics, clinical outcomes, and seasonal incidence. Statistical analysis was used to identify trends and correlations within the data.

Results: The majority of malaria cases (65%) occurred in children under five years old, with *Plasmodium falciparum* being the predominant parasite identified. Seasonal peaks were noted just before the monsoon season, indicating a significant environmental impact on transmission rates. Mortality rates were higher among the youngest age group, reflecting the severe impact of the disease on this population.

Conclusion: The study highlights the urgent need for targeted interventions that address both the medical and environmental factors contributing to high malaria rates among children in Bihar. Strategic improvements in public health education, access to care, and vector control are critical for reducing the burden of this disease.

Keywords: Malaria, Pediatrics, Bihar, Seasonal Transmission.

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Introduction

Malaria continues to be a pervasive public health issue, exerting a profound impact on vulnerable populations across the globe, particularly in tropical and subtropical regions where the disease thrives [1]. Among these populations, children are especially susceptible to the severe manifestations of malaria, including high fever, severe anemia, and cerebral complications, which can lead to high rates of morbidity and mortality if not properly treated. Bhagalpur, a city in the state of Bihar, India, is one such region where malaria remains endemic, posing significant health challenges, especially to its pediatric population [2,3].

Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH) in Patna serves as a pivotal healthcare institution, offering critical insights into the malaria burden within this community [4]. This study, conducted at PMCH, aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of pediatric malaria cases, examining the scope and impact of this disease on children in this area. The primary objectives are to assess the incidence, clinical presentation, treatment outcomes, and factors contributing to mortality and morbidity

among pediatric patients treated for malaria at this facility [5].

This research will employ a retrospective analysis of hospital records to map the trend of malaria infections over recent years, focusing on seasonal patterns, age-specific prevalence, and treatment efficacy [6]. Furthermore, the study will delve into the socio-economic backgrounds of the affected populations, hypothesizing that lower socioeconomic status is a significant risk factor for higher morbidity and mortality rates in malaria cases due to issues such as delayed hospital presentations, lack of access to preventive measures, and inadequate post-treatment care [7,8]. Environmental factors also play a crucial role in the transmission dynamics of malaria. The study will therefore explore the local ecological conditions that may contribute to the proliferation of mosquito vectors, such as stagnant water bodies and inadequate waste management, which are prevalent in resource-limited settings like Patna [9].

The study aims to articulate clear, evidence-based recommendations for local health authorities. These recommendations will focus on improving preventive strategies, such as mosquito control programs and community education regarding malaria symptoms and the importance of early treatment. Additionally, the study seeks to enhance clinical protocols and interventions at PMCH, tailoring them to the specific needs and challenges faced by the pediatric population in this endemic region. By shedding light on the intricate interplay of clinical, socio-economic, and environmental factors that contribute to pediatric malaria in Patna, this study will not only aid in refining local health strategies but also contribute to the broader discourse on malaria control and prevention in similar settings globally.

Methodology

Study Design: This research was structured as a retrospective cohort study, enabling the exploration of patterns and outcomes of pediatric malaria cases over a specific timeframe. The retrospective design facilitated the utilization of existing medical records to examine and analyze the clinical presentations and progression of malaria without influencing patient care or outcomes.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH) located in Patna, Bihar. PMCH serves as a central healthcare facility in the region, providing a significant dataset of malaria cases due to its role as a referral center. The timeframe for the study, from June 2015 to May 2017, was chosen to capture data across different seasonal cycles, which is crucial in understanding the transmission dynamics of malaria.

Participants: A total of 95-96 pediatric patients were included in this study. This sample size provides a robust base for statistical analysis and conclusions about the patterns of malaria in this demographic. The participants were patients treated for malaria at PMCH during the study period.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: The inclusion criteria were pediatric patients diagnosed with malaria, confirmed through laboratory tests such as microscopy or rapid diagnostic tests. Exclusion criteria included patients whose malaria diagnosis was not confirmed by laboratory tests, as well as any patient records that were incomplete or inaccessible.

Bias: To minimize potential sources of bias, the study employed systematic data collection from hospital records, ensuring consistency in the data reviewed. Selection bias was controlled by including all eligible pediatric cases diagnosed during the study period, and information bias was

minimized by standardized review and extraction of data from patient records by trained personnel.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data on demographics (age, gender, residence), clinical outcomes (recovery, mortality), and socio-economic status (based on address and noted economic indicators) were meticulously extracted from the hospital records. This comprehensive data collection allowed for a detailed assessment of malaria's impact on different population segments within the pediatric group. The analysis also explored potential correlations between socioeconomic status and malaria outcomes.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analyses were conducted using Chi-square tests for categorical data and t-tests for continuous variables. These tests were chosen to evaluate the statistical significance of associations between demographic factors and malaria outcomes. The analysis aimed to identify any statistically significant patterns or trends in malaria morbidity and mortality among the study population.

Ethical Considerations: The study adhered to strict ethical standards, having been reviewed and approved by the PMCH Ethics Committee. All patient data were handled with confidentiality and anonymity. Ethical considerations also included ensuring that the retrospective analysis did not affect the care received by patients or the privacy of their medical information.

Results

The study conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital over two years reveals significant findings regarding pediatric malaria. Notably, children under five years of age are disproportionately affected, representing 65% of all cases, as illustrated in the age-specific distribution of malaria cases. This demographic also experiences a higher mortality rate, with a 6.45% fatality rate among the affected, compared to 2.94% in children aged 5-10 years. Analysis of seasonal variations highlights a critical peak in malaria cases during the months leading up to the monsoon season (March-May), accounting for 38% of the annual case total, suggesting environmental factors significantly influence transmission rates. These data points underscore the urgent need for targeted interventions to address the heightened risk to younger children and to mitigate the seasonal spikes in malaria transmission.

Figure 1: The pie chart depicts the distribution of malaria cases by age group.

Table: Mortality Rates by Age Group

Age Group	Number of Deaths	Mortality Rate
Under 5 years	4	6.45%
5-10 years	1	2.94%

Discussion

This study at Patna Medical College and Hospital highlights the burden of pediatric malaria in Bihar, with significant implications for public health strategies and clinical management. The disproportionately high incidence and mortality of malaria among children under five, and the pronounced seasonality of transmission, offer critical insights into the epidemiology of malaria in this region.

Comparatively, recent research in similar endemic settings has shown that the vulnerability of young children to malaria, particularly from *Plasmodium falciparum*, remains a consistent finding. For instance, a study conducted in Sub-Saharan Africa in 2022 reported that children under five years of age were the most affected group, corroborating our findings regarding the age-specific risk of severe malaria outcomes (WHO, 2022) [10,11]. Additionally, the seasonal peak observed in our study aligns with global patterns, particularly in regions with monsoon climates, where malaria transmission intensifies just before and during the rainy season, as noted in studies from Southeast Asia (Lancet, 2021) [12,13].

Our study's finding that 65% of malaria cases occurred in children under five emphasizes the critical need for targeted preventive measures and rapid treatment interventions in this age group. The

The table summarizes the mortality rates associated with malaria within the same age groups. The mortality rate is significantly higher in the under-five age group, aligning with their higher incidence of severe malaria symptoms as noted in clinical observations. This table provides critical insight into the lethal impact of malaria, particularly on younger children.

Figure 2: The bar graph visualizes the seasonal variation in malaria cases.

high mortality rate among these young children, despite available treatments, suggests gaps in access to care or in the timely utilization of malaria control measures. This is further compounded by socio-economic factors, as most affected children come from rural areas, highlighting disparities in healthcare access and the influence of socioeconomic status on health outcomes [14,15].

Looking forward, this study underscores the necessity of integrating more robust vector control measures with community-based education programs. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies to track the effectiveness of such interventions over time [16,17,18]. Additionally, there is a compelling need for operational research into the barriers to accessing and utilizing malaria prevention and treatment services, particularly in rural settings [19]. Innovations in rapid diagnostic tools and mobile health technologies could also play a transformative role in enhancing timely diagnosis and treatment, thus reducing the burden of malaria in vulnerable populations [20].

By continuing to build on the foundational data provided by studies like ours, and by integrating comparative data from similar epidemiological settings, healthcare strategies can be refined to target the most at-risk populations more effectively. Furthermore, the introduction of newer, more effective vaccines, currently under development,

could offer hope for a significant reduction in malaria morbidity and mortality among children in endemic regions [21].

Conclusion

The study conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital over two years underscores the critical public health challenge posed by malaria in pediatric populations in Bihar, particularly affecting children under five years old. Our findings reveal that these young children are at a heightened risk of severe outcomes from malaria, with a significant number of cases occurring during the pre-monsoon and monsoon months. This highlights the need for targeted health interventions and enhanced preventive measures, especially in rural areas where access to healthcare and malaria prevention strategies remains limited. Consequently, it is essential to bolster community health education, improve diagnostic and treatment services, and strengthen vector control programs to effectively reduce the malaria burden in this vulnerable demographic.

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